

THE NEED FOR TRAINING TEACHERS IN MODERN CONDITIONS

Bozorova Madina Makhmudovna

Senior teacher at Samarkand state architecture and civil engineering university

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***Abstract.** The article is devoted to the analysis of the specifics of professional and pedagogical activity, the directions, types and forms of professional development of teachers of professional education; to the general determination of the importance of continuing education in the professional and pedagogical sphere.*

***Keywords:** qualification, professional training, teacher, professional standard.*

We live in a constantly changing world. In the context of Education State Standards of Uzbekistan society needs competent, highly professional specialists who can successfully fulfill themselves in life. The modernization of the general education school is an integral part of the renewal of the entire education system. At the same time, the teacher has been and remains the central figure in the implementation of school reforms.

Now we need a professionally competent teacher with great creative potential, high spiritual and moral qualities and new pedagogical thinking, a new vision of the school, the student, the world around.

No one doubts that the future of our society depends on the children sitting at the school desk. It is necessary that students learn not only to answer the questions that the teacher puts before them, but also to independently formulate them for themselves in the process of studying the material. The teacher stands on an equal footing, directs, organizes. Only with such an approach can one educate a student who thinks freely, who is not afraid to express and defend his opinion. A modern teacher should educate the student in the need for education. At the same time, the teacher not only has to teach children, but he himself is able to learn from his students.[1]

The teacher, being in a creative search, constantly feels the need for advanced training. In fact, the professional growth of a teacher is carried out throughout his life. In my opinion, advanced training, implemented every five years, is no longer enough to acquire new knowledge for the successful implementation of one's professional activity. In addition, in my opinion, it has a number of disadvantages as:

- traditional forms and models of advanced training are ineffective and costly;
- innovative educational technologies and their application should be taught not at a lecture in the classroom, but using an activity approach;
- the complexity of organizing retraining and advanced training of teachers with a complete separation from their professional activities;
- the unified nature of advanced training programs that do not reflect the needs of specific teachers.[2]

Therefore, the most relevant, in my opinion, is professional development through self-education. Therefore, even at the university, it is necessary to prepare the future teacher for independent continuous improvement of their professional qualifications. A student who has graduated from a university should have competencies that allow him to improve his qualifications when it becomes necessary and to do this without interrupting his professional activity, using for

this purpose the potential of a new information and communication educational environment, in particular, Web technologies.

Significant changes should take place in the system of advanced training of the teaching staff. Personalized systems for advanced training and retraining of the teaching staff using ICT tools should be developed, tested and implemented, conditions should be created for training teachers to work in the information and communication educational environment, new approaches to collective forms of professional self-education based on Web technologies should be introduced.[3]

The national educational initiative "New Uzbekistan" sets the task of improving the system of advanced training for teachers. At the same time, advanced training and retraining programs built on a modular basis should flexibly change and adapt to the pedagogical goals of teachers, which in turn are determined by the educational needs of students. Particular attention, in my opinion, is occupied by professional pedagogical competencies associated with the need to ensure the advanced development of professional activity.

Increasing the professional competence of a teacher is difficult, in my opinion, for a number of reasons. There is a gap between the psychology of the student himself and the psychology of the teacher. I would like the teacher's work to be a holistic model that would encompass all aspects in unity: the process and result of labor, the specifics of labor in different conditions. Such a model would allow, in my opinion, to see one's work as a whole and evaluate each manifestation of one's skill or quality in a general context, which would help to increase the teacher's professional competence.

A special role, in my opinion, is given to the activities of the teacher to improve their skills in the process of developing and conscious use of student-centered educational technologies. The process of professional development of a teacher in the course of his work on the development of educational technology with a personal orientation implies the conditions under which the teacher's work on the development of educational technology effectively affects the growth of his qualifications. This will happen if:

- the teacher's work will be associated with technology that is adequate to the current socio-pedagogical situation and modern educational goals, namely, with student-centered technology;
- there will be a rethinking of the values and personal meanings of pedagogical activity and a methodical reflection of one's own pedagogical experience will be carried out;
- work on the development of personality-oriented technology will be carried out in unity with work to strengthen the value-sense orientation of the content of education;
- in the process of mastering student-centered educational technology, personal opportunities and creative abilities of the teacher will be realized;
- the technology will be based on taking into account the characteristics of the educational situation in the classroom, the characteristics of students and their real learning opportunities, the characteristics of the content of education and the personal capabilities of the teacher in its implementation.

So, in my opinion, in order to improve the professionalism of the teacher and increase his need for advanced training:

- a systematic approach is needed in terms of improving the professional level of teachers;
- it is necessary to involve teachers more actively in the process of reforming school education;

- it is necessary to focus on meeting the real needs of the school;
- network interaction is necessary;
- improve teaching methods using modern educational technologies, ICT, Web-technologies;
- to improve the system of attestation of teachers;
- it is necessary to develop means (educational content) that allow self-improvement;
- work on changing the teacher's consciousness, the formation of a new pedagogical thinking (the teacher acts as a tutor organizing the learning process);
- it is important that the teacher's work be associated with technology that is adequate to the modern socio-pedagogical situation and modern educational goals, namely, with student-centered technology;
- advanced training and retraining programs built on a modular basis should be flexible and adapt to the pedagogical goals of teachers, which in turn are determined by the educational needs of students;
- improve professional pedagogical competencies related to the need to ensure the advanced development of professional activities.
- it is necessary to take into account advanced foreign and domestic experience;
- it is necessary to continue and improve the holding of professional creative competitions for teachers;
- it is necessary to intensify the activities of internship sites on the basis of educational organizations;
- to renew the institution of mentoring;
- it is necessary to raise the social status of the teacher.

Thus, professional development of a teacher plays an important role in his activities such as expands career prospects, introduces the teacher with new, innovative learning technologies, contributes to the effectiveness of pedagogical interaction with various categories of students, helps to improve, deepen knowledge in specific professional matters. Modern educational standards require a specialist to be highly and the quality level of work performance and constant updating, updating knowledge and skills in a particular area.

And to implement this task in the modern education system, various programs for advanced training are being developed and implemented.

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4. Savina Svetlana Vladimirovna (savinas@list.ru) 8-925-303-22-43, FGOBU VPO Financial University under the Government of the Russian Federation, Senior Lecturer of the Computer Science and Programming Department.